

Supporting Information

Cold and Hot Spots: from Inhibition to Enhancement by Nanoscale Phase Tuning of Optical Nanoantennas

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METHODS

Preparation of DBT single molecule near-field samples. As fluorophore, we have chosen Dibenzoterrylene (DBT) single molecules embedded in Anthracene (AC) thin crystals. DBT is highly photostable in AC crystals, with well-known absorption and emission spectra and a close to unity internal quantum efficiency, when embedded in high quality organic matrix.^{1,2,3} DBT exhibits an absorption spectrum in the near-infrared with a maximum absorption peak at 750 nm,^{4,5} The emission spectrum is slightly red-shifted with respect to absorption, with the main emission peak at 790 nm.⁶

The DBT single molecule samples are fabricated by spin coating of a solution on a thin (170µm) glass coverslip.⁶ For the solution preparation first we dissolve anthracene (AC) in diethyl ether with a concentration of 2.5 mg/ml and 10 µl/ml of benzene. The last serves to improve the quality of the crystals obtained from the spin-coating process.⁶ Then we disperse DBT in toluene in a concentration of 10 µM. At this point we dilute of a factor of 100 the DBT

solution in the AC one. This final solution is spin coated on a coverslip with a speed of 2000 rpm and of 7000 rpm. Indeed such speed strongly influences the final layer thicknesses, that are respectively of ~ 40 and ~ 20 nm. The thicker samples present homogeneous AC crystals with lateral size in the order of hundreds of micrometers. The thinner samples present relatively smaller and more fragmented crystals (*lateral size* < 10 μm). In the AC crystals the molecules are oriented parallel with each other, in the horizontal plane.⁶ We use the thinner samples for hotspots visualization experiment, because the Z distance for antenna near-field interaction is < 30 nm. We use the thicker samples for cold spots visualization since the antenna near-field interaction range extents for many tenths of nanometers in Z direction. The chosen concentration corresponds to a typical single molecule sample, where in average molecules are separated enough in the AC crystals to be imaged individually. To make sure that we work with single molecules we perform time-trace measurements, observing single step bleaching process, typical for emission of single molecules.

Figure 1: Determination of DBT molecule orientation in AC crystals. (a) Laser reflection image showing the AC crystal on glass. (b, c) Fluorescence images of the same AC crystal shown in (a) with excitation polarization perpendicular and parallel to the DBT transition dipole, corresponding to the fluorescence images with minimum and maximum emission, respectively. Weak spots are single DBT molecules, brighter spots aggregates of a few molecules.

DBT molecules embedded in AC crystals are all oriented along the crystal axis, in the xy plane, with the molecules parallel to each other^{1,2}. Thus, the DBT-AC system is particularly advantageous for our purpose of using x-oriented molecules, aligned parallel to the antenna. In order to know

the exact orientation of the molecules in the AC crystals in the xy plane we perform excitation polarization measurements, progressively rotating the polarization of illumination light. In Figure 1 we show the experimental procedure followed for the in-plane orientation determination. Figure 1a shows a laser reflection contrast image of the AC crystal. The crystal is distinguished from the rest of the sample because of its higher laser light reflectivity, which creates the contrast. In Figures 1b & 1c we show fluorescence images of the same AC crystal in Figure 1a, with DBT molecules embedded, illuminated with polarization respectively perpendicular and parallel to the molecules. For the sake of simplicity we only show images with minimum and maximum fluorescence emission, that correspond to perpendicular and parallel orientation of illuminating light polarization with respect to the molecular dipole orientation. Knowing the antenna orientation we are able to control antenna-molecule relative orientation.

Furthermore, we get an additional confirmation of the fact that we work with single molecules oriented parallel to antenna from our near-field images. In fact, the shape, lateral size and intensity of the features depend on the number, orientation and relative positions of emitters in the scanned zone.⁷ Only for a single emitter oriented parallel to antenna we observe the typical pattern with 2 lobes at a distance slightly larger than the antenna length, as reported in Figure 4 of main document.

Antenna preparation. The antenna material, size and aspect ratio are designed in order to have a tunable resonance, controlled by length, as shown in Figure 2. The antennas are fabricated at the apex of a tapered optical fiber. The fiber is used as a support for the antenna, which is scanned in close proximity of the sample surface allowing the near-field interaction with the emitters. The antenna is fabricated out of a thin layer of aluminum deposited at the apex of the fiber, by means of Ga⁺ and He⁺ focused-ion-beam-milling (FIB). This reliable and reproducible method allows the fabrication of nanoantennas as scanning probes with a specific 3D orientation. The antennas are fabricated with a lateral size of 50x50 nm² and different lengths. The orientation is flat with respect to the horizontal plane. A detailed description of the flat antennas fabrication procedure can be found in reference.⁷

Figure 2: Dependence of nanoantenna resonances with respect to length. FDTD calculated dipolar and quadrupolar resonances of nanoantennas used as near-field probes. Each antenna supports a dipolar and a quadrupolar resonance, located in different areas of the spectrum. At 750 nm wavelength the dipolar resonance ($\lambda/2$) is supported by a 200 nm length antenna, while the quadrupolar resonance (λ) by a 480 nm length one. The 300 nm length antenna at 750 nm wavelength acts like a hybrid antenna. The nanoantenna is excited asymmetrically with a dipolar emitter source. The probes are located at 10 nm Z distance from a glass substrate.

Scanning Antenna Microscope. The experiments are performed with a custom-built near-field microscope. It consists of an inverted confocal microscope, with a scanning probe head. The system allows the independent scanning of both the probe and the sample by means of a shear-force feedback mechanism. The feedback is based on custom-built electronics that detect the phase between the driving signal, oscillated by means of a piezo with a voltage of $\sim 50\text{ mV}$, and the phase response of the tuning fork itself. Any interaction between the tip and the surface results in a change of phase that is used by the feedback loop in order to keep the antenna-surface z distance constant with $<$ nanometer accuracy. Such shear-force feedback mechanism does not provide a direct measurement of the absolute antenna-surface z distance. However, based on various near-field measurements and z -scans we estimated such distance to be of approximately 10 nm. The force feedback system automatically provides topographical images of the surface, with a resolution in z direction of $\sim 1\text{ nm}$. This way the near-field coupling between the antenna and the emitter located in the AC crystal is permitted, with nanometer precision. Two main scanning configurations are possible: the probe can be scanned over an emitter continuously illuminated inside the diffraction-limited spot, or the sample can be scanned with the probe located in close proximity of the surface centered on the diffraction-limited spot.

The emitters are illuminated with light of 750 nm wavelength (10 nm FWHM), focused using a 100X 1.3 NA oil immersion objective. The system is excited with linear polarization along antenna probe axis. The laser power before the objective is $\sim 0.25\ \mu\text{W}$ for the fluorescence measurements and $\sim 20\ \mu\text{W}$ for lifetime measurements, corresponding to power densities of 0.5 and 40 kW/cm^2 , resp. In the collection path, 776 nm and 780 nm long pass filters are used in order to filter out the reflected excitation light. The fluorescence is confocally imaged onto two fast avalanche photodiodes (APD) (PD-050-COD, Micro Photon Devices, Bolzano) for single-photon counting and photon correlation.

Figure 3: Lifetime analysis through time-gating and fit of the photon histogram. Sketch of a typical photons histogram distribution with respect to arrival time. For fitting the decay rate, we apply a time-gate and only consider the photons arriving into the interval between t_{start} and t_{stop} . (b) Photon histograms of an uncoupled and a coupled case. The solid lines represent single exponential fit obtained after rejecting the photons with arrival time < 0.3 nsec after the laser pulse. The lifetime is longer for the coupled case. (c) Lifetime graphs of the coupled and uncoupled cases with respect to t_{start} . The two lines cross only in the yellow area, which corresponds to the antenna luminescence time interval. (d) Normalized χ^2 dependence with respect to t_{start} . The green area corresponds to a region where the normalized $\chi^2 < 0.5$. In general, the normalized χ^2 gets reduced with the decrease of t_{start} , with the exception of $t_{\text{start}} < 1$ nsec, that corresponds to an *arrival time* < 0.3 nsec after the laser pulse (0.7 nsec). Choosing $t_{\text{start}} = 1$ nsec we can exclude the peak of metal luminescence and minimize the normalized χ^2 .

Photon Time-Gated Imaging and Lifetime Maps. The DBT single molecules are excited with a picosecond pulsed tunable laser ($\lambda = 750 \text{ nm}$, pulse width ~ 70 and 30 ps respectively, SuperK Extreme, NKT Photonics), with 80 MHz repetition rate. The use of time-correlated single-photon counting (TCSPC) correlator (PicoHarp 300, PicoQuant GmbH) allows the recording of the absolute arrival time of the emitted photons on the APDs, with respect to the excitation pulse with 8 ps resolution. The instrument response function is of $\sim 50 \text{ ps}$ full-width half-maximum for light of a wavelength of 750 nm. Customized software allows the synchronization of this equipment with the scanning antenna microscope, in order to obtain intensity maps with photons histograms recorded at every pixel.

The idea of time-gated detection is depicted in Figure 3a), where there is sketched a typical photons histogram in logarithmic scale, with photons arrival times taken with respect to the laser pulse (black vertical line), located shortly after zero time. The technique consists in considering only photons arrived into a specific time interval, included between t_{start} and t_{stop} , the green area. In Figure 3b) and c) there are presented photons histograms of a coupled and an uncoupled case with solid lines representing single exponential for lifetime calculation. We notice from the photons histograms fits how the antenna-emitter coupled case shows a longer lifetime. In the coupled case shown in Figure 3b) we also notice the presence of a sharp peak in photons histogram for very short arrival times. Such peak is due to fast antenna metallic self-luminescence, a process that happens in a few hundreds of femtoseconds. Since this contribution is one order of magnitude smaller than a typical single molecule fluorescence as DBT, we don't see it for the uncoupled case in Figure 3b). Nevertheless, because of the fact that we deplete excitation enhancement in the coupled case with our out-of-resonance probe, the molecule emission is also reduced and the antenna self-luminescence peak dominates molecule fluorescence. An effective way to exclude such contribution and retrieve molecular lifetime is to time-gate the data and reject the photons with very short arrival time. In Figure 3c) there are reported the lifetimes of the coupled and uncoupled case with respect to t_{start} . Decreasing t_{start} the lifetime values converge to 5.2 nsec and 4.5 nsec. For $t_{\text{start}} < 1 \text{ nsec}$, yellow, area, we notice a strong decrease of coupled case lifetime. This effect is due to introduction in the photons histograms of peak located at very short arrival time, due to antenna self-luminescence previously described. Hence we reject such artifact excluding yellow region in lifetime

calculation. It is interesting to note how, regardless of t_{start} choice, Figure 3c) shows that coupled case lifetime is always longer than uncoupled one, validating our emission inhibition conclusion. In Figure 3d) we plot the trend of normalized χ^2 with respect to t_{start} . Such graph shows how decreasing t_{start} we also decrease normalized χ^2 , improving fitting precision. The green area in Figure 3d) correspond to normalized $\chi^2 < 0.5$, therefore presents more stable fitting results than the red one. The best fit condition is found for normalized χ^2 minimum for $t_{start} = 1$ nsec, that is the time-gating parameter that we have chosen for our lifetime calculation. The analysis of lifetime calculation reported in Figure 3 supports our conclusion that our out-of-resonance 300 nm length antenna can induce partial emission inhibition on a single DBT molecule.

Figure 4: x-component scattered field phase horizontal maps. FDTD calculated X-component phase horizontal maps of the light scattered by the antenna, 15 nm under it. (a), (b) and (c) Phase maps of respectively a $\lambda/2$ antenna of 200 nm length, a 300 nm length antenna, and of a λ antenna of 480 nm length. The phase values indicated correspond to the hot/cold spot positions.

Numerical Simulations. We solve Maxwell's equations using a finite-difference time domain (FDTD) commercial solver (Lumerical Solutions, Inc., Vancouver). For the simulations in excitation, the tightly focused laser beam has been modeled as a plane-wave. In general the AC layer has been modeled as glass, with a refractive index $n = 1.5$. The dipolar antenna is modeled as an aluminum nanorod of 50×50 nm² lateral size and different lengths. The near-field probes are designed as a single nanoantenna connected to a glass support through a thin titanium adhesion layer. The probe resonance is calculated taking into account the presence of the probe support and of glass. The antenna is located 10 nm on top of AC layer. In order to quantify the

excitation enhancement/reduction, the total x-component electric field intensity $|E_{x,tot}|^2$ across the antenna and AC layer has been calculated by FDTD and normalized to the x-component incoming field intensity $|E_{x,inc}|^2$. Both, the excitation field and the one scattered by the antenna are simulated. The resonances shown in Figure 2 are obtained exciting the antennas using a dipolar emitter located laterally with respect to the probe. In fact, the excitation of symmetric modes (so called dark modes) as the quadrupolar one, would have been impossible using the typical plane-wave used for the other simulations in excitation. As presented in figure 2, both dipolar and quadrupolar resonances redshift increasing antenna length. In general, for a fixed antenna length, dipolar resonances are redshifted with respect to quadrupolar ones. At the DBT maximum absorption wavelength of 750 nm the dipolar resonance is supported by a 200 nm length antenna, while the quadrupolar one is supported by a 480 nm length probe. A 300 nm antenna has a dipolar and quadrupolar resonances relative red and blue-shifted with respect to 750 nm wavelength. This means that the 300 nm probe is a hybrid one, partially supporting both $\lambda/2$ and λ modes. The dipolar part of resonance gives strength to antenna scattering, while the quadrupolar one makes that scattered light is strongly out-of-phase, as shown in Figure 2. For these reasons our 300 nm hybrid antenna is the most appropriate for strong destructive interference of the excitation field, hence for generation of cold spots.

In figure 4 some of the XY horizontal 2D maps of E_x phase shown in first figure of paper are presented. Such monitors are located 15 nm under antenna probe, 5 nm inside AC layer. Figure 4 shows how antenna scattered light has a subwavelength structured phase and how such phase is both position and antenna length (resonance) dependent.

For the simulation of molecule emission, the source is modeled as a dipolar emitter, aligned along X direction. For the simulations of decay rates Γ and lifetime τ 2D maps, the emitter is simulated as a dipole emitter with internal quantum efficiency $\eta = 1$ and it is located inside the AC layer, below the antenna. For the decay rate and lifetime ($\tau = \tau_0/\Gamma$) the total power radiated by the emitter alone in AC layer and the one of the emitter located in every specific configuration with respect to the antenna are compared. The ratio between the two powers is the reduction of lifetime at each antenna-emitter position.

The role of the z-field component in the inhibition of emission. We consider the measured lifetime increase in terms of interference with the antenna scattered field at the molecule position. The DBT molecule, as an x-oriented dipole, emits as a Hertz dipole in all directions: the emitted field has x, y and z-components. For the interference effect to influence considerably the emitter decay rate, the scattered and emitted intensities have to be comparable at the emitter position: $I_{scat} \sim I_{emit}$. More importantly, the relative phase of the scattered light at the emitter position will determine for each component of the field whether interference is constructive or destructive. Since our x-oriented emitter is aligned with the antenna axis, the y-component of the scattered field is null for symmetry reasons. Furthermore, according to our simulations the x-component $I_{x,scat}$, parallel to the antenna surface, is many orders of magnitude smaller than the emitted field intensity $I_{x,emit}$ at emitter position. Hence, we conclude that interference mediated by the x-component is also negligible. In contrast, as the z-component $I_{z,emit}$ is relatively small in close proximity to the x-oriented emitter, it can efficiently interfere with the scattered z-component $I_{z,scat}$ and locally modify LDOS. Here, in Figure 5 we show x-profiles, along the antenna axis direction, of the z-component of the intensity $I_{z,scat}$ and phase ϕ_z at emitter position $z = 50 \text{ nm}$. The intensity exhibits two maxima at a distance of 200 nm, in correspondence the slow-decay spots in main paper Figure 5. At the positions of the maxima $\phi_z = \pi$, indicating that the z-component of the scattered field is largely out-of-phase with the emitted field at the emitter position. This analysis shows that, for an x-oriented dipolar emitter, the decay rate increase/decrease is mainly due to constructive/destructive interference of the z-field component between scattered and emitted field at dipole position, confirming that the measured slow-decay spots, hence the partial emission inhibition, observed in our data is due to destructive interference between the emitted and antenna-scattered z-fields at the DBT molecule position.

Figure 5: Spontaneous emission inhibition of a single molecule by a detuned antenna. Profiles of the scattered z-field intensity and phase ϕ_z for an emitter at distance $z = 50 \text{ nm}$ to a 300 nm long detuned Al rod antenna. The z-field intensity shows two maxima at a distance of 200 nm, strongly out-of-phase with incoming beam ($\phi_z = \pi$), resulting in a lowering of the local density of states, i.e. slower decay rate. Simulations performed for an emitter at 780 nm wavelength, with an internal quantum efficiency of 1.

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